

The Significance of Ratifying International Laws and Resolutions on Anti-Corruption in Uzbekistan: Economic-Political and Socio-Legal Mechanisms

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Abstract: The article is devoted to an analysis of legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan on counteraction against corruption. The article provides the classification and review of the anti-corruption legislation of Uzbekistan. The article also deliberates about the measures taken by Uzbekistan to implement relevant international legal standards into the national legal system¹.

Key words: corruption, codes of ethical conduct, anti-corruption policy and legislation, United Nations Convention against Corruption, Transparency International, public control, legal culture, e-government.

Corruption is one of the most pressing global issues, and the international community has adopted various laws and resolutions to combat it. By ratifying these international instruments, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to develop and implement effective strategies to fight corruption.

Economic-Political Mechanisms

* Developing and implementing state programs and strategies for combating corruption.

* Coordinating the anti-corruption activities of state authorities and governance bodies.

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* Activating social and political movements against corruption.

Corruption is one of the serious impediments for effective development of a state and represents a huge social threat. Therefore, the development of legal anticorruption mechanisms is becoming one of the main priorities of state policy. Now, despite all the efforts made by the state, corruption has created a real threat to the national security of the country. It damages the stability and security of society, undermines the principles of good governance, the market economy and threatens the stability of state institutions. Hence, readiness for an effective fight against it is considered by the world community as the main indicator of the state's advancement, its commitment to democratic values. In recent years, the leadership of Uzbekistan has been consistently and persistently taking necessary measures to further strengthen the rule of law to prevent the penetration of corruption into public institutions, politics and the economy. The president of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev pays great attention to this issue. During his speech at the a joint meeting of the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis he stressed that “[w]e must take decisive measures to counter and prevent corruption in our society, various crimes and offences, ensure the implementation of the law on that the punishment for a crime is inevitable” . Legal methods of fighting corruption should begin with the improvement of legislation. Legislative support for combating corruption is one of the most important conditions for successfully combating this phenomenon. In this regard, at the legislative level, there is a constant search for a balance of legal regulation of the most effective measures to combat this corrosion of public, state and managerial relations.

The objectives of the scientific article were to conduct a legal review of the anti-corruption legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a comparative legal analysis of the anti-corruption legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a number of foreign countries, the consideration of the basic theoretical and legal approaches to

the content of the anti-corruption struggle, and the identification of conditions for the effectiveness of national anti-corruption legislation².

Summary:

In conclusion, the ratification of international laws and resolutions on anticorruption is of great importance for Uzbekistan. It enables the country to significantly improve its economic-political and socio-legal mechanisms for fighting corruption. As a result, Uzbekistan can achieve a substantial reduction in the level of corruption and ensure the effective protection of the rights and interests of its citizens

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